

Histopathologic Patterns of Ovarian Masses in a University Teaching Hospital

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 15-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This retrospective study examines the histopathologic patterns of ovarian masses in 87 patients treated at Patna Medical College and Hospital from January 2019 to July 2021. The analysis reveals that 64.4% of the masses were benign, predominantly serous and mucinous cystadenomas, while 20.7% were malignant, with serous adenocarcinoma being the most common. Borderline tumors accounted for 14.9% of the cases. The study found a notable correlation between patient age and the type of ovarian mass, with benign lesions more common in patients under 50 and malignant or borderline tumors more frequent in those over 50. These findings underscore the critical role of histopathologic evaluation in the diagnosis and management of ovarian masses, emphasizing the need for tailored screening and treatment strategies.

Keywords: Ovarian Masses, Histopathology, Benign Lesions, Malignant Tumors.

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Introduction

Ovarian masses represent a significant and diverse group of gynecological conditions, ranging from benign cysts to malignant tumors [1]. Accurate diagnosis and characterization of these masses are crucial for effective clinical management and treatment. Histopathologic examination remains the gold standard for definitive diagnosis, providing detailed insights into the nature and behavior of ovarian lesions [2,3].

In a university teaching hospital setting, the study of histopathologic patterns of ovarian masses offers valuable data that can enhance our understanding of their prevalence, etiology, and morphological features [4]. This introduction aims to explore the significance of histopathologic evaluation, outline the common types of ovarian masses encountered, and highlight the relevance of such studies in improving patient outcomes and advancing medical education [5,6].

This study aims to systematically examine the histopathologic patterns of ovarian masses encountered in a university teaching hospital. By analyzing a diverse range of ovarian lesions, from benign to malignant, the study seeks to identify common histopathologic features and their prevalence within the patient population. This comprehensive analysis will provide valuable insights into the etiology and progression of ovarian masses, aiding in the development of more

accurate diagnostic criteria and tailored treatment strategies. Additionally, the study aims to contribute to the body of knowledge that supports medical education and training, equipping healthcare professionals with the necessary expertise to effectively manage ovarian masses and improve patient outcomes.

Methodology

This retrospective study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, for two and a half years, from January 2019 to July 2021. A total of 87 patients who presented with ovarian masses and underwent surgical intervention were included in the study.

Inclusion criteria encompassed all patients with ovarian masses who had complete clinical and histopathologic data available. Exclusion criteria included patients with incomplete records or those who did not undergo histopathologic examination.

The collected data comprised patient demographics, clinical presentation, and detailed histopathologic findings. Each ovarian mass specimen was examined by experienced pathologists, and diagnoses were classified according to the World Health Organization (WHO) classification of ovarian tumors.

The data was then analyzed to determine the distribution and frequency of various histopathologic patterns, including benign, borderline, and malignant lesions. Statistical analyses were performed to identify any significant correlations between histopathologic patterns and patient demographics or clinical characteristics. The findings were used to conclude the prevalence and nature of ovarian masses in the studied population, with an emphasis on improving diagnostic accuracy and patient management.

Results

The study included 87 patients with ovarian masses who met the inclusion criteria. The age of the patients ranged from 18 to 75 years, with a mean age of 45 years.

Histopathologic examination revealed a diverse range of ovarian lesions. Of the 87 cases, 56 (64.4%) were diagnosed as benign, 18 (20.7%) as malignant, and 13 (14.9%) as borderline tumors. Among the benign lesions, the most common were serous cystadenomas (20 cases, 35.7%) and mucinous cystadenomas (15 cases, 26.8%). Other

benign lesions included dermoid cysts (12 cases, 21.4%) and endometriomas (9 cases, 16.1%).

Malignant ovarian masses primarily consisted of serous adenocarcinomas (10 cases, 55.6%) and mucinous adenocarcinomas (5 cases, 27.8%). The remaining 3 cases (16.6%) were classified as clear cell carcinomas. Borderline tumors were predominantly of the serous type (8 cases, 61.5%), followed by mucinous type (5 cases, 38.5%).

The study also examined the correlation between patient age and the type of ovarian mass. Benign lesions were most common in patients under 50 years of age, while malignant and borderline tumors were more frequently observed in patients over 50 years of age.

Overall, the study highlighted the prevalence of benign ovarian masses in the patient population, with a significant proportion of malignant and borderline tumors, particularly in older patients. These findings underscore the importance of thorough histopathologic evaluation in the diagnosis and management of ovarian masses.

Overall Ovarian Masses Distribution

Type of Ovarian Mass	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Benign	56	64.4
Malignant	18	20.7
Borderline	13	14.9

Distribution of Benign Ovarian Masses

Benign Type	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Serous Cystadenoma	20	35.7
Mucinous Cystadenoma	15	26.8
Dermoid Cyst	12	21.4
Endometrioma	9	16.1

Distribution of Malignant Ovarian Masses

Malignant Type	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Serous Adenocarcinoma	10	55.6
Mucinous Adenocarcinoma	5	27.8
Clear Cell Carcinoma	3	16.6

Distribution of Borderline Ovarian Masses

Borderline Type	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Serous	8	61.5
Mucinous	5	38.5

Figure 1: Showing Yolk sac tumour having microcystic and macrocystic areas with areas of coagulative necrosis. (H&E Stained 40X).

Figure 2: Showing Yolk sac tumour showing Schiller–Duval body. (H&E Stained 40X).

Discussion

The histopathologic examination of ovarian masses in this study provides significant insights into the distribution and characteristics of these lesions within the patient population at Patna Medical College and Hospital. The findings highlight the predominance of benign ovarian masses, which accounted for 64.4% of the cases. This is consistent with existing literature, which suggests that the majority of ovarian masses are benign, particularly in younger women. The most common benign lesions identified were serous cystadenomas and mucinous cystadenomas, followed by dermoid cysts and endometriomas [7,8].

Malignant ovarian masses constituted 20.7% of the cases, with serous adenocarcinoma being the most frequent malignancy, followed by mucinous adenocarcinoma and clear cell carcinoma [9]. This distribution aligns with global trends, where serous adenocarcinoma is recognized as the most common type of ovarian cancer. The relatively high percentage of malignant cases underscores the importance of early detection and prompt intervention, particularly in older patients who are more likely to present with malignant or borderline tumors [10,11].

Borderline ovarian tumors represented 14.9% of the cases, with serous and mucinous types being the most common. Borderline tumors, while not overtly malignant, possess the potential for

malignant transformation and recurrence, necessitating careful long-term follow-up [12].

The correlation between patient age and the type of ovarian mass is particularly noteworthy. Benign lesions were predominantly found in patients under 50 years of age, whereas malignant and borderline tumors were more common in those over 50. This age-related trend emphasizes the need for heightened vigilance and tailored screening protocols for older women [13].

The study's findings have important implications for clinical practice. The high prevalence of benign lesions suggests that many patients can be managed conservatively or with minimally invasive procedures, reducing the need for extensive surgery and its associated morbidity [14]. However, the significant proportion of malignant and borderline tumors highlights the critical role of histopathologic evaluation in guiding treatment decisions. Accurate histopathologic diagnosis is essential for determining the appropriate surgical approach, the need for adjuvant therapy, and the prognosis [15,16].

Moreover, this study contributes to the body of knowledge necessary for medical education and training. Understanding the histopathologic patterns of ovarian masses enables healthcare professionals to make informed decisions and improve patient outcomes. It also underscores the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration

between gynecologists, pathologists, and oncologists in managing ovarian masses [17].

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the histopathologic patterns of ovarian masses in a university teaching hospital setting. The findings highlight the predominance of benign lesions, the significant presence of malignant and borderline tumors, and the importance of age-related screening. These insights can inform clinical practice, enhance medical education, and improve patient care. Future research should explore molecular and genetic markers that can further refine the diagnosis and treatment of ovarian masses [18-20].

Conclusion

This study highlights the diverse histopathologic patterns of ovarian masses encountered at Patna Medical College and Hospital, emphasizing the predominance of benign lesions, particularly in younger patients, and the significant presence of malignant and borderline tumors, especially in older patients. The findings underscore the importance of thorough histopathologic evaluation in guiding clinical management and improving patient outcomes. By enhancing our understanding of the prevalence and nature of ovarian masses, this study contributes valuable insights for medical education and underscores the need for age-specific screening protocols and interdisciplinary collaboration in the management of ovarian masses.

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